

HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES AND ORGANIZATIONAL PRODUCTIVITY IN NIGERIA: A STUDY OF IMO STATE POLYTECHNIC, OMUMA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma. This is based on contending issue that human capital development has not been adequately considered paramount in Imo State polytechnic, Omuma Nigeria. The insufficient personnel, inadequate funding, poor infrastructures, corruption and poor motivation of the staff posed treat to efficient human capital development and productivity. Based on this, the study was conducted in order to identify the possible strategies to improve human mental, social, economic and psychologies development to enhance productivity in the organization. Therefore, the researchers made use of both primary and secondary data sources. The primary sources include; questionnaires administration and Empirical review while the secondary sources include; literature review. Human capital theory was used. The population of the study used is 1350 with sample size of 309 calculated with Taro Yamane formula of 5% coefficient error estimated. Simple random probability sampling technique was used to give equal participation to all staff. The hypothesis was tested with the used of standard deviation, and Pearson correlation regression. The study found that funding, infrastructures, single campus initiatives, motivation, utilization of personnel and security strategy necessitate human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma. The recommendations include; that government should as a matter of urgency ensure the provision of sufficient funds to boost human capital development training, infrastructures, standard health care services to enable staff have access to routine service, provide room for motivation of the staff and corrupt free society mostly in the public institutions.

Keywords: *Human Capital Development, Organizational Productivity, Strategies and Education*

1. INTRODUCTION

The need to improve human knowledge for organizational productivity remains sacrosanct. This is because; it engenders creativity, innovation and capacity for mental, social, emotional, psychological stability and development in the organizations. The pace at which such can be realized lies on the policy towards engendering human capital development for organizational productivity. However Imo State polytechnic, Omuma has not been left out of the goals of human

capital development need according to Becker (1964) and Schultz (1961) who stated that for a state to progress politically and socio-economically, the human capacity needs to be developed. World Bank in Mba (2013) stated that ensuring fast economic growth requires three fundamental factors, such as natural capital, physical capital and human capital and among these factors, human capital has a major share of 64% contributions to economic growth. Economic development is in itself the realization of human potential, without which no realized potential would be possible (Piwowar-sulej, 2021). Human resources not physical capital, not income or materials resources constitute the ultimate basis for the wealth of nations. That is why Imo state polytechnic, Omuma has over the years considered trainings of manpower in the various skills acquisition, knowledge building, education and aptitudes as crucial. An improving quality of life by economic development is the result of the development of human capital (Hassan et al., 2019). However, this improves the environment and its developmental strive to the contemporary time where human resources development necessitate the need for capacity building considering the vitality of improving the teaching and learning, skills acquisition, creative enablement and practical use of these attitudes to engender organizational productivity.

Dess and Picken (1999) asserted that human capital consists of the individual's capabilities, knowledge, skills and experience of the company's employees and managers, as they are relevant to the task at hand as well as the capacity to add to this reservoir of knowledge, skills and experience through individual learning. Spacey (2018) defines human capital as the productive capacity of labour. This becomes important because of its ability to improve human skills, teaching and learning, creativity and innovative techniques, exploring, harnessing and utilizing those values for intellectual exercise into production and service for environmental resuscitation, stability and development. This informs Marimuthu et al (2009) to defines human capital as the processes that relates to training, education and other professional initiative in order to increase the level of knowledge, skills, abilities, values and social assets of an employee's which lead to the employee's job satisfaction and performance. World Bank (2021) state that countries investing in people optimally to prevent the hard won human capital gains from being eroded more and builds back better to ensure green, resilient and inclusive development. Frank and Remanke, (2007) stated that human capital is an amalgam of factors such as education, experience, training, intelligence, energy, work habits, trustworthiness and initiative that affect the value of a worker's marginal product. This definition refers to the role of human capital on worker's productivity.

However Josan cited in Odhong and Omolo (2015) argue that organization effectiveness is characterized by competitiveness, innovation and excellence. Competitiveness depends on skills and human capital investment. Human capital investment is characterized by investing in education, health and training; insisting that globalization has resulted in new economy known as knowledge economy in which human capital variables; education and training plays a significant role. Based on the existing literature, analysis that investment in human capital is directly proportion not only with the productivity of the organizations, but trainings, increase productivity by 16% but also, with productivity. This can result to over twice the size of the wages increased because of trainings witnesses in the organization. This is a reflective of human capacity building in Imo State polytechnic that has been enjoying human capital development by training, with daunting challenges on low productivity occasioned by government policy framework on multi campuses system in different senatorial district of the state with administrative dependency at the centre (Omuma). The four campuses face daunting challenges of poor infrastructures, poor funding and incentive for staff motivation as irregular promotion and absence of pension scheme for retired personnel become problem in the realization of the dream and aspirations of human

capital development of the institution. Owing to this development, this research is conducted in order to strategize on the possible measures to achieve the goals of human capital development for organizational productivity in the Institution.

Therefore the specific objective is to examine the strategies to improve human capital developments for organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma. So, the research objectives seek:

1. To examine the strategies necessary to improve human capital development for organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma.
2. To articulate the relationship between human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma.

The research questions are:

1. What are the strategies necessary to improve human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma?
2. What are the relationship between human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma?

The hypotheses of the study include the followings;

H0₁ There are no relevant strategies to improve human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma.

H0₂ There is no relationship between human capital developments and organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma.

The study is essential for academic development because of its tendency of adding more ideas, knowledge, creativity and innovation into existing literature. It is relevant as it closes the gap incurred by previous scholarly writing and identifies solution to problems. It can as well help to improve education, healthcare and knowledge building, creativity, skills acquisition and outputs production. It addresses the problems that affect human capital of the organization, employees and how it improves organizational productivity. It will help the policy makers, leaders, managers and administrators of Imo state polytechnic, Omuma to be able to identify the human resources of the society, its utilization by exploring, exploiting, harnessing and galvanizing and also improve the organization productive performance. The relevance of the study states that this study improves the existing literature on four areas: First, It identified the constraints of human capital development. Secondly, it articulates the effects of human capital development and examined the indices and parameter for measuring human capital performance of the institution.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Capital: Human capital is the degree of investment given to education, skills acquisition, knowledge building and its correspondence capacity to engender capacity building among the staff in the organization. Marimuthu et al (2009) defines human capital as the processes that relates to training, education and other professional initiative in order to increase the level of knowledge, skills, abilities, values and social assets of an employee's which lead to the employee's job satisfaction and performance.

Human Capital Development: Human capital development is the series of the trainings given for manpower development in the organization. Ughamadu and Ozioma (2016) assessed the state of human capital development in Nigeria with a view to determining the extent to which it can support

the Nigeria manufacturing sector in achieving objectives established for it by the countries policy document, vision 2020. Training at this point entails a process of inculcating knowledge, ideas, skill and competence in staff (persons) in order to improve productive service. Training and development are activities aimed at imparting to employees the requisite skills, knowledge and behavioral conduct necessary for their jobs (Keys & Wolfe, 1998). Trainings provide knowledge and skills which enable the completion of employees' tasks. Development is the series of trainings which employees undergo while preparing for career progression. It also involves development of employees abilities and potentials through learning both practical and theoretically.

Human Capital Strategy for Organizational Productive Performance

In all these above, development of human capital requires a combination of organizational learning strategy, strategies to enhance individual learning, effective execution of training workshops and formal off the job training and blended stratifies, consisting of all these above Armstrong in Ameyaw, (2010, p, 51). World Bank (2021) states that countries investing in people optimally to prevent the hard won human capital gains from being eroded more and builds back better to ensure green, resilient and inclusive development. At this point, there are five variables that affect employees' performance in the organization. Such according to Sheri-Lynne and Parbudyal, (2007) are: coaching, training and development, empowerment, participation and delegation.

1. **Coaching** is an intervention that seeks to bring an employee to his predetermined performance level in his current function within an organization. It is guided, structured and requires continues monitoring (Colomo & Casado, 2006). To realize this noble objective, the organization appoints a coach for the employee with the main purpose that the coach will work with the employee to correct work-related defects and improve employee skills, knowledge and abilities to enhance performance. Coaching enables correction, re-engineering mental, social and psychological condition of an employee into a stable state of mind.
2. **Training and development:** Training and development is an activity aimed at imparting to employees the requisite skills, knowledge and behavioral conduct necessary for their jobs (Keys and Wolfe, 1998). Trainings provide knowledge and skills which enable the completion of employees' tasks. Development is the series of trainings which employees undergo while preparing for career progression. It also involves development of employees abilities and potentials through learning both practical and theoretically.
3. **Empowerment:** Energizing people through training, skill acquisition and knowledge building enhances administrative acumen and management capacity in order to take initiative and responsibility of the organizational productive performance. Kamal,et al. (2008) opined that empowerment is the transfer of responsibility and operational management from line manager to operational teams and individuals. This phenomenon provides freedom in the work place and enables the restoration of confidence among the employees which increases the capacity of the human resources of the organization.
4. **Participation:** - Participation involves the inclusion of the employees in the decision and policies making of the organization. This gives room to democratic principles and knowledge sharing with best decision making polices towards achieving organizational goals and objectives. Participation enhances social skills, leadership skills, cross fertilization of knowledge, creative and innovative ideas and team spirit (sportsmanship) which promotes the organizational productivity, peace building, effective and efficient service delivery and profitability that spur the organization to greater height.

5. **Delegation:** - Delegation is the transfer of responsibility from superior to the subordinate. When a leader/manager delegate authority to the subordinate employee to perform a function in place of him; the targets if properly delegated and acted, can lead to a considerable level of organizational performance. Xiyangzhang et al, {2017} state that delegation of administration promotes feedback, seeking behaviour by psychologically empowering subordinates. So, power distance moderates the relationship between delegation and feedback seeking behaviour. Baker, {2022} opined that delegation is a process by which a leader transfers responsibility for successful execution of a task to another. Therefore, Douglasbasil,{2019}holds that delegation is the ability of the managers to share his burden with others. It consist of granting authority or the right to decision making in certain defined areas and charging subordinates with responsibility for carrying through an assigned task. However, it is the duty of the organization to set targets and prioritize those targets to meet the expected goals and objectives of the organization. Be that as it may, Harrison (2005) articulated the five steps organization should follow in setting their priorities. Such include:
- i. **Raise Awareness:** Organization should raise awareness of the need for a learning culture that leads to continuous improvement.
 - ii. **Development of Managerial competency:** Ensuring the development of managerial competency in order to become actively involved in learning that leads to knowledge creation.
 - iii. **Improve Learning Capacity:** Organization should expand as a matter of fact the learning capacity of the institution in order to continue enhancing knowledge and skills which engender productive performance of the employees.
 - iv. It should be focusing absolutely on the organizational knowledge of the workers not limiting to critical personnel.
 - v. **Harness e-Learning to knowledge sharing and creation:** Organization should try to harness e-learning to knowledge sharing and creation to improve continuously organizational productive performance.
 - vi. **Funding of the organization:** Resources make organizational policy and programmes on infrastructures and other developmental strived possible. It also promotes effective and efficient organizational productivity and capacity building.
 - vii. **Infrastructural development:** Provision of roads network, electrification, pipe borne water, Hospitals and related services, schools, markets, Library and research centre etc. the enable knowledge, creativity, and human sustainability and also capacity building in the organization.

How to improve Human capital Management

Gaurav, [2022] states the seven strategies to prepare for the future of human capital management. Such include;

- i. Embrace technology and analytics
- ii. Understand how the company succeeds
- iii. Stay focused on people
- iv. Be ready for the new workforce
- v. Market a modern benefits package
- vi. Stay abreast of compliance issues
- vii. Be certified or update your skill set.

2.1 THEORETICAL LITERATURE

The human capital theories are known by the following leading proponents among them are; Jacob Mincer, (1958), Theodore Schultz, (1961) and Gary Stanley Becker in (1964). These theories have fundamentally rooted from macro-economic development theory captured in Becker's classic book captioned "human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis of education". In the theory, Becker viewed different kinds of capitals which include; schooling, computer training courses, expenditure on medical care, important of punctuality and honesty as indicators that improve health, raise earnings and add values to personality thereby enhances productive performance. Becker opines that investment in human could be viewed as similar to investment in other means of production like factories or mines. That is because they raise the earnings, improve health and add to a person's lifetime. This is because; economists' regards expenditures on education, training and medical care as investment on human capital (Becker, 2011). Further stressed that economic growth cannot be explained by the growth of physical capital and technological innovation rather the growth of human capital. Becker, (1993) distinguishes firm specific human capitals from general purpose human capital. The firm specific human capital include expertise obtained through education and training in management information systems, accounting procedures or other expertise specific to a particular firm. The general purpose human capital is knowledge gained through education and training in areas of value to a variety of firms such as generic skills in human resource development.

Theodore Schultz, (1961) contend that a society should invest in its citizens through expenditures on education, training, research and health that enhance their productive capacity. He believes that human capital is the added value that people bring in an organization. Schultz (1979) opined that human capital involves the increase investment in education and training of the individuals and individual abilities can be enhanced through education and training that bring about effective change in the performance of jobs. In his further studies, he set out to map how the rate of return from education could be calculated in countries with different levels of income, different attitudes to forgoing earnings to develop human capital (Severine & Lila, 2009). Therefore, it is consented that the theory acknowledges well trained personnel as a great asset to the organization. It is a potential based of an organization and acknowledges, organizational competitive advantage to the direct function of its human capital base available. Shultz, (1981), in his book "take into account the innate and acquired skills' those are important and may invest to expand and will form the human capital. So, 'investing in people (human capital) is the only source of economic growth in a modern economy'. He maintains that investing in skills and innate values promote organizational productivity. Human capital theory is a theory on finance and economics. This theory articulates that companies have an incentive to set productive human capital of their existing employees. It is also a concept that recognizes labour capital and posits that human beings can increase their productive capacity through greater education and skills training. They further analyze that as the world build up on physical capital, the opportunity cost of going to school reduced. This makes education vital component of the workforce to enable innovation or creativity.

Jacob Mincer was considered by many as the father of the modern labour economics. He was one of the leading members of Chicago school of economists whose work 'investment in human capital and personal income distribution' in his journal of political economy (1958) attracted much profound impact. He accompanied Gary Becker in the development of empirical foundations of human capital theory and revolutionizes the field of labour economics. His ground breaking work was on schooling, experience and earning published in (1974) used data from 1950 and 1960

censuses to relate income distribution in America to the varying amounts of education and on the job training among workers. In his calculations, annual earnings rose by 5 to 10 percent in the 1950s and 1960s for every year of additional schooling. Mincer's work impacted greatly to labour economics thereby model wages as a function of human capital in statistical estimation. That made Mincer's work such as schooling and work experience as variables use in measuring human capital. However, it is very clear that human capital is all about the employees and not the employers. His very simple formulation basically fits the data for understanding how earnings are related to educational attainment in virtually every country in every time period (Lawrence, 2006)

2.2 EMPIRICAL STUDIES

In the empirical analyses; Asghar et al. (2017) studied human capital and labour productivity in district Lahore. In the course of analyzing this relationship, cross sectional study was conducted and data was collected from 243 firms, which include manufacturing, trading and service sector. The empirical analysis reveals that all the sectors have heterogeneous effect of human capital on labour productivity. Education appears to be significant and positively related to labour productivity in all the sectors with greater effect in manufacturing sector. The skills and trainings have also noticeable effect on labour productivity. This acknowledge the fact that education, skills acquisition and trainings are essential tools for human capital development in Imo state polytechnic Omuma inspite of poor funding, inadequate infrastructures, lack of adequate motivation of the workers. Alika & Aibieyi, (2014) studied human capital; Definitions, Approaches and management dynamics. In the course of the study, the researchers highlighted the values, importance of human capital to management, individuals and all other interested in the development of their workforce with a view to increase organizational performance. The approaches used fund as its root in business economics theory. Definitions of human capital were made to understand the nature, status and importance of human capital in all facets. They further assert the problems of definition, poor funding of human capital development and lack of trust. The researchers did well in identifying funding as the pillar for human capital development in the organization. States further the challenges of funding the organization as the problem of organization towards achieving effective human capital development and organizational productivity mostly Imo State Polytechnic. The strategies for human capital development to organizational productivity were not covered in the study. They did not examine how human capital development can be controlled for greater organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic and how human capital development affects the productivity indices of the staff of the polytechnics, its constraints in the tertiary education mostly the polytechnics subsector; such as Imo State Polytechnic. The constraints associated with the labour wage/salary, economic recession witnessed recently. The effects of electricity supply on the capital expenditure in which the rate of capital expenditure reduction determines the degree at which human capital development improves the manufacturing sector of the economy. Based on the above development that the study was conducted to consider the above and also ensure strategic measures towards which human capital development are achieved in the organization.

3 METHODOLOGY

The research design used in this study is descriptive research were population, sampling, methods of data collection and data analysis adopted. The structured questionnaires were designed to reflect the research questions used in the study. The population is made up of 1350 being the population

of both academic and non-academic staff of the polytechnic. The sampling Technique used by the researchers is simple random probability sampling technique. This technique gives equal opportunity for all respondents to participate in the research study. The sample size of the study was drawn from the population of the staff of the Institution which is 1350 and calculated with Taro Yamane formula as shown:

$$\begin{aligned}
 n &= \text{Sample size} & 1 &= \text{Constant} \\
 N &= \text{population} & E &= \text{coefficient error by 5\%} \\
 n &= \frac{N}{1+N \times (e)^2} & n &= \frac{1350}{1+1350 (5)^2} & n &= \frac{1350}{1+1350 (0.05)^2} & n &= \frac{1350}{1+1350 \times 0.0025} \\
 n &= \frac{1350}{1+1350 \times 0.0025} & n &= \frac{1350}{1+3.375} & n &= \frac{1350}{4.375} & n &= 308.57 & n &= 309
 \end{aligned}$$

The researchers used two methods in data collection: The primary data collection methods and the secondary data collection methods. In the primary data collection, the researchers administered questionnaires to the respondents to gather information. The questionnaire was accompanied by letter addressing the respondents to assist by responding to questionnaire administer. The secondary data collection was conducted: In that case, the researchers gathered information through the existing literature such as; journals, extraction from textbooks and internet materials respectively. **The Validity and Reliability of the Measuring Instrument:** The researchers adopted face/content validity and construct validity to measure the extent to which the data for the study are reliable. In the face validity, well-structured questionnaire instruments were carried out by the researchers. The researchers also ensured that the items in the questionnaire were in conformity with the items in the objectives of the study, research questions and research hypothesis which are the representativeness of sampling adequacy of the content {the substance, the topic, the issue}. The researchers also constructed instrument of responds for the respondents in a four (4) likert scale. This questionnaire purported to cover and test as it appears to test participants. The test-retest methods were used to confirm the reliability of the study. It could be observed in the consistency and dependability of the result given by the respondents while responding to the questionnaires and hypothetical studies. The result of the study is adjudged to be consistency, dependable and credible when questionnaires administered and the responses given by the respondents agreed majorly with and disagreed with the research questionnaires, objectives and hypotheses of the study. Here, the instrument has produced consistency the same result over time. In the first test, the researchers distributed hundred and fifty (150) questionnaires to the public (Imo state polytechnic staff) and in return, hundred and forty (140) were recovered and recorded. While analyzing the questionnaires, it is observed that the respondents' maintained consistent views over time.

Retest method, one months later, hundred and fifty nine (159) questionnaires were distributed to the public (Imo state polytechnic staff) and in return, hundred and forty five (145) were recovered and recorded. While analyzing the questionnaires recovered, it is observed that the results are correlated with the earlier test results, which implies that there is high coefficient of correlations between the two results hence the used of SPSS was made paramount in calculation of mean of the scores, standard deviation and Pearson correlation coefficient which give room to conclusion that the results of the tests are reliable. The data were analyzed using the descriptive approach. The study used Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, Pearson correlation coefficient and statistical tables to analyze the questionnaire. Pearson correlation was used to test hypotheses. The data were obtained from questionnaire administered to the respondents.

The data presentation, analysis and interpretation are done with the use of simple percentage, mean and standard deviation and Pearson correlation regression analysis. The study starts with the analysis of the data presentation, analysis and interpretation with hypothetical analysis of the study. Bellows are the tables

3.1 Theoretical Framework

Gary Stanley Becker in (1964).theory has fundamentally rooted from macro-economic development theory captured in Becker's classic book captioned "human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis of education". In the theory, Becker viewed different kinds of capitals which include; schooling, computer training courses, expenditure on medical care, important of punctuality and honesty as indicators that improve health, raise earnings and add values to personality thereby enhances productive performance. Becker opines that investment in human could be viewed as similar to investment in other means of production like factories or mines. That is because they raise the earnings, improve health and add to a person's lifetime. This is because; economists' regards expenditures on education, training and medical care as investment on human capital (Becker, 2011). Further stressed that economic growth cannot be explained by the growth of physical capital and technological innovation rather the growth of human capital. Becker, (1993) distinguishes firm specific human capitals from general purpose human capital. The firm specific human capital include expertise obtained through education and training in management information systems, accounting procedures or other expertise specific to a particular firm. The general purpose human capital is knowledge gained through education and training in areas of value to a variety of firms such as generic skills in human resource development.

Assumptions of human capital theory

It states that the composition of the employee in form of skills, knowledge, and abilities is the key to organizational performance.

Investing in skills and innate values promote organizational productivity. It is also a concept that recognizes labour capital and posits that human beings can increase their productive capacity through greater education and skills training. Human capital development is the employee knowledge, skills; know how, good health and education that enhances personal and organizational productivity.

Organization invests in its citizens through expenditures on education, training, research and health that enhance their productive capacity. Human capital is the added value that people bring in an organization.

Critics

1. The critics of human capital theory argue that it is flawed overly simplistic and confounds labour with capital. One of the critics of human capital theory by name, Richard freeman, and a Harvard economist in 1976 argues that human capital only acted as a signal about talent and ability, real productivity came later through training, motivation and capital equipment and concluded that human capital should not be considered as the factors of production.
2. The sociologists and Anthropologist criticized the human capital theory with their assertions that it offers extremely simple principles that purported to explain ones wages

as a determinant of productivity and income of an organization and argued further that the productivity differences between individuals cannot be measured objectively.

The Strengths of Human Capital Theory in Education and Policy Making

1. It is used in education research and policy making. It helps the policy makers and researchers evaluate the relationship between the educations and training as inputs and economic and social benefits as outputs. Since the assumption stated that increase amount of schooling will bring growth in higher individual wages, Gross domestic product and increase in citizens participation, crime reduction and adequate healthcare services. Therefore, this enables the policy makers evaluate relatively the efficiency of public programs that encourage education (Schooling).
2. It provides a useful avenue for understanding how policy can be developed to promote individuals investment in their education. It reviews that embarking in further education (schooling) involves both cost that is spending (sacrificing at present and benefiting through higher wages in future) within individual level. Therefore, adopting human capital theory in this study will help the policy makers develop rational policies geared towards providing avenues for students' loan and enrolment programmes to change individual costs and benefits calculation by reducing the short costs in order to encourage the likelihood of pursuing education increasingly.
3. Human capital theory can be used to address individual social investments in education, such as the quality knowledge/investment in education that are productive and the best time for education and policy development best to reduce the costs of education.
4. It helps to increase the creative and innovative knowledge and how to utilize the knowledge to further productivity, investment, growth and development of the society.

Importance of human capital theory

- i. Adopting human capital theory and principles enhances knowledge; skills and education which provide sustainability and development thereby provide opportunities for future generation.
- ii. It provides good opportunity for education and trainings among individuals and organization thereby promotes economic growth and productivity. This is because; long term economic growth depends to greater extent on the improvement on human capital. A good education, creativity or innovative workforce fosters labour productivity and economic growth and development.
- iii. It provides good opportunities for well-paid job/employment: Building upon the human capital theory enables knowledge and trainings that can lead to provision of quality employment. This is because the acquisition of high skilled and creative workforce has increasing opportunities for self-employment or good employment contacts and job provision.
- iv. It enables the beneficiaries of the abilities who are surrounding with limited raw materials to utilize their skills and knowledge in order to ensure economic growth. For instance; countries like Japan and Koreans who are surrounded with limited natural resources always rely on human capital for advancement and capacity building.

4. RESULTS AND THE DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 4.1 Occupational Qualification of Respondents

Response	Number Distributed	%	Number Returned	%	Number not Returned	%
Academic Staff	149	48	134	43	15	5
Non Academic Staff	160	52	151	49	18	3
Total	309	100	285	92	24	8

Source: field study, 2024

Note, that out of 309 questionnaire distributed, 285 were collected for interpretation of the respondents opinion in the questionnaire administered, 149 respondents representing 48% were academic staff of the Polytechnic, while 160 respondents representing (52%) were non-academic staff of the Polytechnic respectively.

Research Question one: What are the strategies adopted by Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, to improve human capital development and organizational productivity?

S/N	The strategies for human capital Development and organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic Omuma are as follows:	Strongly Agreed	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
A	Funding	76(27%)	46(16%)	14(5%)	149(52%)
B	Provision of incentives for motivation of the workers	79 (28%)	61(21%)	43(15%)	102(36%)
C	Provision of health care services to the personnel	59 (21%)	103(36%)	19(7%)	104(36%)
D	Provision of Infrastructures facilities to the organization to engender human capital development to organizational productivities	60(21%)	63(22%)	60(21%)	102(38%)
E	Provision of well trained personnel in the organization	68(24%)	151(53%)	15(5%)	51(18%)

Source: field study, 2024

In research question one option one 76 respondents representing (26%) agreed that funding is one of the strategies to improve human capital development in Imo state polytechnic.46 respondents representing(16%) strongly agreed while 14 representing 5% and 149 representing52% disagree and strongly disagree on the notion respectively. Meanwhile, 163(57%) said that funding of the organization is not strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma while 122(43%) agreed that funding improve human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic Omuma.

In research question one option two, 79 respondents representing (28%) agreed that the provision of incentive for motivation of workers is one of the strategies to improve human capital

development in Imo state polytechnic. 61 respondents representing (21%) strongly agreed while 43 representing 15% and 102 representing 36% disagree and strongly disagree on the notion respectively. Meanwhile, 145(51%) said that incentive to workers motivation in the organization is not strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma while 140(49%) agreed that incentive to workers motivation improve human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic Omuma.

In research question one option three, 59 respondents representing (21%) agreed that the provision of healthcare services is one of the strategies to improve human capital development in Imo state polytechnic. 103 respondents representing (36%) strongly agreed on it while 19 representing 7% and 104 representing 36% disagree and strongly disagree on the notion respectively. Meanwhile, 162(57%) said that the provision of healthcare services is one of the strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma while 123(43%) disagreed that healthcare services improve human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic Omuma.

In research question one option four` `60respondents representing (21%) agreed that Provision of Infrastructures facilities to the organization to engender human capital development to organizational productivities in Imo state\polytechnic. 63respondents representing (22%) strongly agreed while 60 representing 21% and 102representing(38%)disagree and strongly disagree on the notion respectively. Meanwhile, 162 (59 %) said that Infrastructures facilities of the organization is not strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma while 123 (43%) agreed that Infrastructures facilities improve human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic Omuma.

In research question one option five, 68respondents representing ((24%) agreed that Provision of well trained personnel in the organization is one of the strategies to improve human capital development in Imo state polytechnic. 151respondents representing (53%) strongly agreed on it while 15representing (5%) and 51 representing (18%) disagree and strongly disagree on the notion respectively. Meanwhile, 219 (77%) said that Provision of well trained personnel in the organization is one of the strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma while 66 (23%)\ disagreed that Provision of well trained personnel in the organization improve human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic Omuma.

Table 4.2: Mean responses on the Strategies adopted by Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, to improve Human Capital Development and Organizational Productivity

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Remark
	The Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, has effective strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity	18	114	21	132	2.06	1.06	Disagreed
i.	The Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, provides adequate health care services to facilitate human capital development and organizational productivity	59	103	19	104	2.41	1.18	Disagreed

ii.	The Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, has provided infrastructures for improve human capital development	60	63	60	102	2.28	1.16	Disagreed
iii.	The Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, has well-trained personnel to implement strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity.	68	151	15	51	2.13	3.8	Agreed
iv.	The Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, has adequate incentives to drive employees to improve human capital development and organizational productivity.	79	61	43	102	2.41	1.23	Disagreed
v.	The Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, provides funding that will enhance human capital development and organizational productivity.	76	46	14	149	2.17	1.31	Disagreed
Grand Mean						2.24	1.20	Disagreed

Table 4.3 showed the strategies adopted by Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, to improve human capital development and organizational productivity. With the respective item means falling below 2.5, the table accounted that the Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma does not adopt effective strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity, does not provide adequate resources to facilitate human capital development and organizational productivity, does not provide infrastructures for effective and efficient human capital development and organizational productivity, have well-trained personnel to implement strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity, does not have adequate incentives to drive employees to improve human capital development and organizational productivity, and does not have policies and procedures that are conducive to human capital development and organizational productivity.

The Important Relationship between Human Capital Development and Organizational Productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma Correlations

		Strategies adopted by Imo State Polytechnic	Organizational Productivity
Strategies adopted by Imo State Polytechnic	Pearson Correlation	1	-.930**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	285	285
Organizational Productivity	Pearson Correlation	-.930**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	285	285

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2.5 showed the summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis on the relationship between strategies adopted by Imo State Polytechnic, to improve human capital development and organizational productivity. The result showed the value of the R-square -0.930

was roughly -93% contributions of strategies adopted to improve human capital development to organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma. The result also showed that the p (significant value=0.00 is less than 0.05 at 285 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis three is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. Therefore, there is a significant negative relationship between the strategies adopted to improve human capital development to organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma.

4.1 DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The study is on human capital development strategies for organizational productive performance in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma within the period of 2017-2024. The following findings were made:

- i. Inadequate funding and its effect to human capital development and organizational productivity: Most of the respondents consented that when there are poor funding in both administrative and academic areas, human capital development need of people will be affected seriously. It is worthy of note that 122(43%) personnel consented that Imo state polytechnic provide funding for human capital development while 163(57%) personnel rejected the view insisting that poor funding affect human capital development in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma
- ii. Therefore, there is need for adequate health care services to facilitate human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma. Therefore, 162(56%) consent that Imo state polytechnic provides health care services to boost human capital development and organizational productivity while 123(44%) rejected the assertion accordingly.
- iii. Poor infrastructures and no enabling environment for effective monitoring and evaluation systems to ensure human capital development achieve the organizational productivity consequence to inefficiency. It is worthy of note that 162(56%) stated that Imo state polytechnic Omuma has not provided adequate infrastructures to enable it ensure organizational productivity against 123(44%) that agreed that Imo state polytechnic has adequate infrastructures to ensure the provision of human capital development to organizational productivity in the state.
- iv. 219(77%) agreed that there is well-trained personnel as a strategy to implement human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma but the study observed inadequate funding for effective implementation of the skills knowledge acquired to enhance productivity in the institution while 66(23%) disagreed with the notion
- v. 145(51%) stated that there is Inadequate incentives to drive employees to improve human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma while 140(49%) disagreed with the notion. Therefore adequate incentives should be made to drive employees to improve human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma.

4. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The work actually examined the strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic Omuma. From the analysis, it was discovered that education,

infrastructural facilities, motivations, funding, and good leadership influence organizational productivity.

Therefore, the study concludes that any organization whose investment strategies anchored on human resources must consider training, education, funding, motivation, infrastructures and good leadership as an opportunity to increase long term productivity. Therefore enhancing staff motivation through trainings and funding with the provision of good leadership in the organization engender productive performance. The engagement of the employees in institutional productivity will be possible with high range of motivation through funding, infrastructures; motivation and job security are the strategies to boost human capital development in Imo State Polytechnic Omuma. Therefore: staff motivation ensures adequate payment of the salaries, wages, allowances and pensions including routine staff trainings to boost morale, creativity and administrative proficiency. Infrastructures which is one of the bones of human capital development is lacking which need to be provided sufficiently to address impending organizational productive challenges in Imo State polytechnic, Omuma. There is government undue interference in the institution which affects the human capital need of the organization. Undue leadership interference from external environment of the institution affects the staff performance. Therefore effective monitoring and evaluation systems for human capital development and organizational productivity will be assured in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma. While there should be adequate training of personnel to implement strategies for human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic, Omuma. Therefore, to boost human capital development towards enhancing organizational productivity, more investment on human capital is required, promotion of work environment, developing evaluation and incentive systems and the provision of strong support for staff trainings and development of the institution remain sacrosanct. Funds need to be provided to enhance human capital development and organizational productivity.

4 Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings; the following recommendations were made:

1. The government of Imo state should ensure adequate and regular motivation and remuneration of staff (human capital) by ensures regular payments of salaries, wages, bonuses and other remuneration packages and also ensures routine training, skills acquisition, knowledge building capacity and development. This will improve morale capacity to work hard, committed spirit of service and effective and efficient service delivery among the staff of the institution and organizations in general.
2. Both the government of Imo state and private sector must understand the need for infrastructural facilities and provide it for the institutional growth and development.
3. Health care services should be considered as a priority for every staff in both public and private sectors of the economy. At this juncture, both government and private sector should do the needful by the provision of good and sophisticated health care equipments, machines and other important gadgets and ensure standard training and development of the health workers and students to ensure capacity building and reduction in mortality rate of personnel. The health care infrastructures/equipments remain essentials.
4. Fund should be made available for human capital development including the education of the personnel to enable the provision of essential knowledge and creativity that can yield innovation and services in the organization.

5. Both the Public and the Private sectors should join hands in the provision of infrastructures for human capital development to thrive in the organization.

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